

POLYPHONIC ANALYSIS OF PRESIDENT FERDINAND MARCOS JR.'S POLITICAL DISCOURSE

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the polyphony in the inaugural speech of President Ferdinand Marcos Junior. This investigation, though it was delimited to the political discourse or address of the late President Ferdinand Marcos, reveals that the Inaugural speech of Ferdinand Marcos Jr. is polyphonic, with the predominant voice of his father and the secondary voices of former President Duterte and Filipino nurses. To fulfill the aim of the study, a Qualitative Descriptive Analysis was used to analyze President Marcos Jr.'s speech, applying Bakhtin's polyphony and Austin's illocution act from Speech Act Theory. The analysis involved investigating the inaugural speech of Marcos Jr. and using the speeches of his father and other related articles to trace the different voices. The researchers applied the Speech Act theory but only the illocutionary act as it deals with the intentions of an utterance. The study found that Ferdinand Marcos Jr.'s speech was polyphonic, thus making it persuasive. The study recommends using other speeches, relatives, and political leaders to make discourse more polyphonic. Also, the inclusion of Polyphonic markers can contribute to more conclusive results.

Keywords: *Discourse, Illocution Act, Polyphony, Speech, Speech Act Theory, Voice*

INTRODUCTION

Political figures convey their plans and thoughts to people through effective language, making them persuasive. To be convincing, they must appear sincere and fully committed to their cause and sound plausible, fair, and on the side of the good. (Biria & Mohammadi, 2012). Also, language is a political figure's tool to shape citizens' directions and beliefs. Politicians' speeches usually contain ideological, philosophical, charismatic, and factual statements convincing people to support them. In this case, Garifullina et al. (2021) explained that an inaugural speech is essential in influencing his audience since a country's president not only states his plans for the future but positions himself as a government leader. The discourse of a president is a special kind of political communication.

In addition to that, a unit of speech communication is the utterance. According to Russian philosopher Mikhail Bakhtin (1986), words and sentences develop into utterances when expressed to a specific hearer or audience. An utterance, then, is related to its speaker and hearer/s. Its meaning is context-specific as it relates to its speaker and the concrete reality where it is uttered. Each utterance is a response to other utterances. It may be a form of support for, rejection, or argument against another utterance. When a speaker produces an utterance using a previous speaker's utterance, the current speaker supports or argues against the previous speaker's utterance. He or she may supplement it with his or her ideas to clarify viewpoints. This is why an utterance reflects different speakers' ideas.

Moreover, when a speaker expresses an utterance to hearers, he or she considers the hearers' possible reactions. In advance, the speaker thinks of arguments that would justify his or her claims. He or she considers how hearers' knowledge, beliefs, and experiences would influence their reactions to his speech. How a speaker's utterance expresses a reaction to a previous speaker's speech and how a speaker considers the possible reactions of hearers explain the dialogic nature of utterances. Every utterance interacts in different ways with its referent, with other words that refer to the same thing and other referents, and with the speaker himself. An utterance is usually influenced by viewpoints and values related to its referent. This interaction of voices or consciousnesses in an utterance makes it polyphonic.

Equally important is the term polyphony. Polyphony refers to the multiple voices; polyphony is the understanding of the utterance. In understanding polyphony, the intention and thought of the utterance or action are essential. Those voices are the focus of the researcher. This research analyzes President Marcos Jr.'s inaugural speech at the National Museum on June 30, 2022. His speech was about 25 minutes long. Some of the things he discussed were his priorities and promises as president. The term 'unity' is its theme. It can be observed that parts of President Marcos Jr.'s inaugural speech resemble his late father's inaugural speech. One part where he mentioned the people wanting a better life was stated as "pangarap ninyo ay pangarap ko. (Your dreams are my dreams) How can we do it together?" This is similar to the late president's "This is your dream and

mine. By your choice, you have committed yourselves to it. Come then, let us march together towards the dream of greatness" (Bacilig, 2022).

Research on the polyphonic nature of speeches delivered by political figures has been conducted, but these were speeches addressed by foreign political leaders to their respective nations. This study aimed to investigate the voices that constituted President Ferdinand Marcos Jr.'s inaugural speech and discuss the role of these in the speech's appeal to Filipino citizens. The argument is that multiple voices are found in President Marcos Jr.'s inaugural speech. The researchers chose the inaugural speech of Marcos Jr. and are inclined to use such political discourse that resonates with different points of view of other people; it is in the researchers' interest to analyze it as no local politicians' speeches are analyzed using polyphony.

Research Questions

The study aimed to investigate the different voices or consciousnesses in President Marcos Jr.'s inaugural speech. It addressed the following questions.

1. What utterances of President Marcos Jr. suggest the inclusion of other consciousnesses in his speech?
2. What could be President Marcos Junior's intentions in including other voices or consciousnesses in his speech?

METHODOLOGY

This study on the Polyphonic Analysis of President Ferdinand Marcos Jr.'s discourse, notably his inaugural speech, was a descriptive analysis that employed Mikhail Bakhtin's concept of polyphony. This study is qualitative since it attempted to analyze the speech of President Ferdinand Marcos Jr. as polyphonic and dialogic. Through descriptive analysis, different voices were identified in his inaugural speech. Also, the intentions and purposes behind Ferdinand Marcos Jr.'s utterances were discussed, considering his role as the speaker and the social context that affected his utterances. Related articles were used to support the analysis of his utterances or the voices in his inaugural speech.

The speech "The Inauguration of Ferdinand Romualdez Marcos, Jr., 17th president of the Republic of the Philippines," can be found on the website <https://pbbm.com.ph>. The researchers chose this specific speech because it resembles how Bakhtin viewed Dostoevsky's novels.

Regarding the data analysis, the researchers first read and annotated the chosen statements from Marcos Jr.'s inaugural speech. Then, they identified the different themes from the chosen utterances. The developed coding scheme uses a printed copy of Marcos Sr.'s speeches, highlighting the traceable utterances or intentions in colors. The

data was coded using tables. Lastly, for the interpretation, the researchers used only one aspect of the Speech act theory, the illocution act.

The president's inaugural speech stirred the idea of a plurality of voices and the interest in investigating these voices. The researchers based the analysis on the four inaugural addresses and the first three SONAs from the late Marcos Sr.

In applying the concept of polyphony, the voices, also called consciousnesses, were identified in the inaugural speech. Since utterances in the speech reminded Ferdinand Marcos Jr. of his father, the late President Marcos Sr.'s utterances, the analysis used the former president's speeches. Further research was news articles that state past and present socio-economic issues of the nation to see how these are reflected in the inaugural speech, articles about other political figures' claims which may have been mentioned or suggested in the speech, and the Filipino people's sentiments expressed through news reports and the social media. The issues discussed in the articles reflect Filipinos' opinions, judgments, and emotions from the different sectors of society, which the utterances in President Marcos Jr.'s inaugural speech react to. The reactions may be in support, evaluation, or argument. Moreover, the reactions may involve solutions to problems.

The analysis further involved using the speech act theory. In discussing the presence of others' consciousnesses in the speech, President Marcos Jr.'s intentions, known as illocutions, and the effects on hearers of the utterances implying these intentions, known as perlocutions, were discussed.

Lastly, this investigation on the polyphony of President Marcos Jr.'s speeches significantly focused only on the Inaugural speeches and the first three State of the Nation addresses of the late President Marcos Sr. as the basis of proving the political speeches of Marcos Jr.'s polyphonic. This study excluded speeches from his mother, Imelda Marcos, siblings, or another political leader since the data analysis predominantly considered the voices of his father alone.

RESULTS

1. *Utterances of President Marcos Jr. Suggesting the Inclusion of other Consciousnesses in his Speech*

Table 1. *Ferdinand Marcos Sr.'s Consciousness in President Marcos Jr.'s Utterances Involving Unity*

Pair	Current President's Utterances Number	Late President's Utterances/ Declarations/ Works	Source (w/ p.no.)
1	"When my call for unity started to resonate with you "At pinakinggan ko ... Pagkakaisa... Pagkakaisa.."	National unity is the covenant..	(Marcos, F.E .,1981, p. 46)

(And I listened ... Unity, Unity...)	... forge a constructive unity and co-exist in purposeful peace.	(Marcos, F.E. 1978, p7)
	"It is our destiny to transform this. nation... no Filipino, no one in the land will be exempt..."	(Marcos F.E. 1969, p. 29)
	"We can never again stand in Alienation from one another..."	(Marcos F.E. 1981, p. 23)
	"... build one nation"	(Marcos F.E., 1981, p. 47)
	"Our goal is to unite, not divide."	(Marcos F.E., 1981, p. 25)
	"We must apply of... Filipino-unity"	(Marcos F.E., 1981, p. 49)
	"We shall move forward as nation"	(Marcos F.E. 1981, p. 51)
	"We are the nation today. With courage and vision we shall be more"	(Marcos F.E., 1981, p. 60)
	"There are not outside saviors; There is only us -The Filipinos."	(Marcos F.E., 1981, p. 63)
	"We can overcome them only If we are gathered to one single. , united nation ..."	(Marcos F.E. 1986, p. 4)
	"...let every man in our republic. , farmer, laborer, ordinary , citizen... part... of this nation"	(Marcos F.E., 1986, p.7)
	"...faith in the Almighty and strengthened by a united people	(Marcos F.E., 1986, p. 11)

Table 1 presents the current president's utterances on unity, the evidence of his father's voice in these, and the sources of these pieces of evidence. Each utterance of Marcos Jr. and that of Marcos Sr. is taken as evidence of the latter's voice or consciousness in the speech, and each is taken as a pair assigned a number.

Table 2. Ferdinand Marcos Sr.'s Consciousness in President Marcos Jr.'s Utterances Involving Change in Leadership

Number	Current President's Utterances	Late President's Utterances/ Declarations/ Works	Source (w/ p.no.)
2	"You picked me to be your servant,"	But you have rejected all these through a new mandate of Leadership	(Marcos F.E., 1965, p. 15)
		You have given me the task of leadership...	(Marcos F.E., 1969, p. 5)
		"Our people sought a new administration in the expectation of a meaningful change..."	(Marcos F.E., 1965, p. 28)

Table 2 shows Marcos Sr.'s utterances addressing himself as the new president and gives a narrative that the Filipinos chose him to be president. Each utterance of Marcos Jr and Marcos Sr. is evidence of his father's voice in the speech.

Table 3. Ferdinand Marcos Sr.'s Consciousness in President Marcos Jr.'s Utterances About Working Together

Number	Current President's Utterances	Late President's Utterances/ Declarations/ Works	Source (w/ p.no.)
3	"We shall be again by radical change in a way the world must now work to recover what we have lost in the fire"	This nation can be great again....	(Marcos F.E., 1965, p. 38)
		But our task is not done... nation building never ends. We must forge on.	(Marcos, F.E., 1969, p. 4)
4	"Come, let us put our shoulders shoulders to the wheel..."	"Come then, let us march together..."	(Marcos F.E., 1965 p. 52)
5	"I will need your help; I want to rely on it".	"The tasks we face are difficult and They will ask sacrifices from all of us.	(Marcos F.E., 1986, p.4)

Table 3 presents the utterances of President Marcos Jr. and the late Marcos Sr., who mentioned the Filipinos working together.

Table 4. Ferdinand Marcos Sr.’s Consciousness in President Marcos Jr.’s Utterances Involving Peace

Number	Current President’s Utterances	Late President’s Utterances/ Declarations/ Works	Source (w/ p.no.)
6	“We all want peace in our land”	“Peace in our time, we declare”	(Marcos F.E., 1965, p. 14)

Table 4 refers to the utterance pair from Marcos Jr. and Marcos Sr. that mentioned “peace.”

Table 5. Ferdinand Marcos Sr.’s Consciousness in President Marcos Jr.’s Utterances Involving the People’s Dream

Number	Current President’s Utterances	Late President’s Utterances/ Declarations/ Works	Source (w/ p.no.)
7	“Ang pangarap niyo ay pangarap ko” (Your dreams are my dreams)	“This is your dream and mine”.	(Marcos F.E., 1965, p. 52)
		“Let us dream the vision of what. could be and not what might have. been”	(Marcos F.E., 1969, p. 14)
		“Thus we prove to our prosperity that our dream was true...”	(Marcos F.E., 1969, p. 32)
		“We shall not merely dream, we shall achieve.”	(Marcos F.E., 1981, p. 42)
		“...redeeming every dream and every aspiration that throughout our national history has fired the hearts and minds of our people”	(Marcos F. E., 1981, p. 26)
		“...this is a beginning and a Change not in dreams and aspirations, but in rededication and reappraisal”	(Marcos F.E., 1981, p. 27)

Table 5 involves the presence of Marcos Sr. in President Marcos Jr's utterance about the dream.

Table 6. Ferdinand Marcos Sr.'s Consciousness in President Marcos Jr.'s Utterances Involving Agriculture

Number	Current President's Utterances	Late President's Utterances/ Declarations/ Works	Source (w/ p.no.)
8	"The role of agriculture cries for the urgent attention ... Food self-sufficiency has been the key promise of every administration. None but one delivered."	"It is a vision of the jungles to the farmer's... for the support for human life"	(Marcos F.E., 1965, p. 44)
		"Self-sufficiency in ...food ...attained in the shortest possible time"	(Marcos F.E., 1966, p. 36)
		"We speak to our farming communities who had been disenchanting by slogans..."	(Marcos F.E., 1981, p. 36)
		"...by farmers rising up to a new dignity as leaseholders, perhaps excited by the innovation..."	(Marcos F.E., 1967, p. 3)
		"In 1966, the government built up new irrigation systems and improved new ones..."	(Marcos F.E., 1967, p. 166)
		"Self-sufficiency in rice and corn. is a major goal of the nation."	(Marcos F.E., 1967, p. 218)
		"... we have succeeded in Producing enough seeds..."	(Marcos F.E., 1967, p. 221)
		"We shall press vigorously the existing efforts... food self-sufficiency on a sustained basis..."	(Marcos F.E., 1968, p. 46)
"... attainment self-sufficiency in food production;"	(Marcos F.E., 1968, p. 49)		

Table 6 presents Marcos Jr's utterance on agriculture, the evidence of his father's voice in these, and the sources of these pieces of evidence.

Table 7. Ferdinand Marcos Sr.'s Consciousness in President Marcos Jr.'s Utterances Involving Education

Number	Current President's Utterances	Late President's Utterances/ Declarations/ Works	Source (w/ p.no.)
9	I am not talking about history. I'm talking about the basics...	"We are committed to provide an educational system..."	(Marcos F.E., 1966, p. 56)
		"Education is central in our plans. for national development"	(Marcos F.E., 1967, p. 246)
		"...lower education add little or nothing to the skilled manpower ... since these skills are produced by vocational school..."	(Marcos F.E., 1967, p. 247)
		"Science teaching is necessary for. our development programs"	(Marcos F.E., 1967, p. 248)
10	"Our teachers ... are our heroes fighting ignorance with poor paper weapons	"Our school system continues to experience difficulties ..."	(Marcos F.E., 1966, p. 25)
		"Education has become more than ever a reality for the poor.... Scholarship funds and student loans for the poor have been extended.	(Marcos F.E., 1968, p. 29)
		"...and the lack of funds has Prevented us from going far... / Public Textbook Program/ ..the vocational education curriculum has been revised to make it more responsive to economic needs / training centers have been established / Board of National Education"	(Marcos F.E., 1968, p. 96)

Table 7 is about the current president's utterance mentioning education, the evidence of his father's voice in these, and the sources of these pieces of evidence.

Table 8. Ferdinand Marcos Sr.'s Consciousness in President Marcos Jr.'s Utterances Regarding Public Health

Number	Current President's Utterances	Late President's Utterances/ Declarations/ Works	Source (w/ p.no.)
11	"...we never got over the pandemic of Poor if any free public health"	"we shall strive to raise the efficiency of our public health service ..."	(Marcos F.E., 1981, p.48)
		"In public health, we have launched. The Malaria Eradication Program"	(Marcos F.E., 1967, p 128)
		"With the substantial increase in rural health units and free medicine for the needy..."	(Marcos F. E., 1968, p 30)
		"...deployment of more physicians, nurses, midwives, and sanitary inspectors in our barrios... more rural health units... for our rural population" / Hospital services were increased and upgraded	(Marcos F.E., 1986, p. 108-109)

Table 8 shows the current president's utterance addressing public health, the evidence of his father's voice in these, and the sources of these pieces of evidence.

Table 9. Ferdinand Marcos Sr.'s Consciousness in President Marcos Jr.'s Utterances Regarding Investors and Business

Number	Current President's Utterances	Late President's Utterances/ Declarations/ Works	Source (w/ p.no.)
12	"Investors are now setting up industries along promising routes built."	"We appeal to the businessmen. nation to harness their best qualities..."	(Marcos 1966 p. 42)
		"We speak to the entrepreneurs throughout our land..."	(Marcos F.E., 1981, p. 38)
		"We have gone out of our way to. invite foreign investments."	(Marcos F.E., 1967, p. 37)
		"...more incentives will be given to domestic investors..."	(Marcos F.E., 1968, p.199)
		"New development opportunities in the Philippines have caught the attention of major investors abroad."	(Marcos F.E., 1968, p. 200)
		The Government Service Insurance.	(Marcos F.E.,

Table 9 presents the current president's utterances mentioning investors and business, the evidence of his father's voice in these, and the sources of these pieces of evidence.

Table 10. Ferdinand Marcos Sr.'s Consciousness in President Marcos Jr.'s Utterances That Mentions His Father's achievements

Number	Current President's Utterances	Late President's Utterances/ Declarations/ Works	Source (w/ p.no.)
13	"My father built more and better roads, produced more rice ..."	Masagana 99 Martial Law	Museum (n.d) Arillo (2015)
		"... self-abnegating leadership... sprung from miracle rice; on every road or bridge. school, hospital, house...we built"	(Marcos F.E., 1969, p. 11)
		"Today, some P250 million is committed. to our rice and corn program..."	(Marcos F.E., 1967, p. 29)
		"We have engaged private capital in the Essential task of building our infrastructure. - mainly roads and bridges"	(Marcos F.E., 1967, p.38)
		"We have built 110 kilometers of concrete. roads as against only 70 kilometers in the years of the previous regime. We have also built 1,948 linear meters of bridges."	(Marcos F.E., 1967, p. 167)
		"We will also build a modern highway system. We made a start last year by constructing 110 kilometers of concrete roads.	(Marcos F.E., 1967, p. 181)
		"This fulfills a historic dream of several generations of Filipinos who equated the solution of the rice problem..."	(Marcos F.E., 1968, p. 6)
		"The government's output of roads , bridges, irrigation ... "	(Marcos F.E., 1968, p. 7)
		"The price of rice has been stabilized, ... The problem now is how to keep the price of rice profitable for the farmers.	(Marcos F.E., 1968, p. 24)
		"More than P520 million have been channeled into the rural areas..."	(Marcos F.E., 1968, p. 33)
		"...providing the necessary infrastructure to support our industrial program an serve the growing population..."	(Marcos F.E., 1968, p. 50)
		Manila North and South Division Roads	(Marcos F.E.,

Table 10 presents the current president's utterance mentioning his father's achievements, the evidence of his father's voice in these, and the sources of these pieces of evidence.

Table 11. Ferdinand Marcos Sr.'s Consciousness in President Marcos Jr.'s Utterances That Mentions Prosperity

Number	Current President's Utterances	Late President's Utterances/ Declarations/ Works	Source (w/ p.no.)
14	"...in a safer, more prosperous country"	"Let us be true to ourselves as the people. of a poor nation struggling to be prosperous"	(Marcos F.E., 1969, p.16)
		"...advance toward a future which will be. bright and prosperous..."	(Marcos F.E., 1986, p. 11)
		"...both the progress and the prospects of the country are encouraging".	(Marcos F.E., 1986, p. 47)
		"We should give our children better education, ...public health services... particularly in rural areas ..."	(Marcos F.E., 1967, p. 255)

Table 11 presents the current president's utterance mentioning prosperity, the evidence of his father's voice in these, and the sources of these pieces of evidence.

Table 12. Ferdinand Marcos Sr.'s Consciousness in President Marcos Jr.'s Utterances That Promote Government and Citizen Working Together

Number	Current President's Utterances	Late President's Utterances/ Declarations/ Works	Source (w/ p.no.)
15	"Now imagine what you and government can achieve together."	"...we shall have once and for all truly a government that is a servant to our hopes and our needs."	(Marcos F.E., 1981, p. 53)
		"...to establish new concepts of cooperation and interaction between government and the people..."	(Marcos F.E., 1981, p. 54)
		"The people's initiative, their caring, and their imagination, as much as those of government, will determine how far... we can achieve..."	(Marcos F.E., 1981, p. 55)

Table 12 presents the current president's utterance regarding the government and Filipinos working together, the evidence of his father's voice in these, and the sources of these pieces of evidence.

Table 13. Ferdinand Marcos Sr.'s Consciousness in President Marcos Jr.'s Utterances Referring to the "road"

Number	Current President's Utterances	Late President's Utterances/ Declarations/ Works	Source (w/ p.no.)
16	"...but I will walk that road With you"	"Come then, let us march together towards the dream of greatness."	(Marcos F.E., 1965, p. 52)
		"I ask you then: let us cross this Frontier"	(Marcos F.E., 1981, p. 66)
		"...advance toward a future which Will be bright and prosperous..."	(Marcos F.E., 1986, p. 11)
		"...guidance to all of us in this sacred and noble mission"	(Marcos F.E. 1986, p. 124)
		"...the great epic of national development..."	(Marcos F.E., 1967, p. 271)
		"Let this be our epic of nation- building"	(Marcos F.E., 1968, p292)

Table 13 presents the current president's utterance mentioning "the road," the evidence of his father's voice in these, and the sources of these pieces of evidence.

Table 14. Other Consciousness in President Marcos Jr.'s Utterances

Number	Current President's Utterances	Late President's Utterances/ Declarations/ Works/ News Articles/ Problems	Source (w/ p.no.)
17	"I thank my predecessor... courage of his hard decisions"	Initial shortage of vaccines/ Successive lockdowns/ Strict social distancing regulations	Presse (2022)
18	"President Rodrigo Roa Duterte	Build, build, build/ People lifted from poverty/. built more and better..." Infrastructure	Lamentillo (2022) / Preses (2022)
19	"Our nurses are the best in the world..."	When the "heroes" "don't feel cared for": The migration and. resignation of Philippine nurses	Alibudbud, 2022

amidst the COVID-19 pandemic

Underpaid and overworked,
Philippine nurses would rather
walk away than work at home.

Chia &
Tolentino,
2021

Table 14 introduces the other voices heard in President Marcos Jr.'s inaugural speech; the evidence of other voices is traced from news articles or programs before his presidency.

2. Intentions to Including Other Voices in the Speech

The second research question aims to answer the following: Given the included voices/consciousnesses in the inaugural speech, what could be President Marcos Junior's intentions in including other voices/consciousnesses in his speech?

Determining the president's intentions in including other voices or consciousnesses in his inaugural speech is based on the concept of illocutionary force, which is an element of the speech act theory. As stated earlier, the illocutionary force is the speaker's intention behind the locution or the utterance. The speaker's intention is suggested by the context of an utterance, including the speaker himself, the hearers, and the situation wherein the utterance was produced.

The inaugural speech marks the beginning of the president's governance. With the 31 million votes that he got, he knew that his call for unity, an affirmation of his father's declaration of unity in "National unity is the covenant between every Filipino, and between the leader and his people," was a factor that won the hearts of those who voted for him. The concept of addressivity is at work here. He knew that reaction to the call for unity would be positive. He restated this as an appeal to their emotions. Appealing to their hearts must have added to the persuasive effect of his speech.

DISCUSSION

Utterances of President Marcos Jr. Suggesting the Inclusion of other Consciousnesses in his Speech

Table 1 is about President Marcos Jr.'s call for unity, and this utterance exhibits the voice of his father, the late Marcos Sr. The call for unity and the words, especially "yearnings," "mirrored your sentiments," and "hopes for family" must have touched the hearts of the Filipinos who voted for him as these words stirred the inner feelings of their need to be understood. These must have also awakened the sense of unity felt during Marcos Sr.'s regime when the differences in socio-economic status felt during the most recent decades in the Philippines were not that strong, if not absent. The utterance of President Marcos Jr.'s –"it echoed your yearnings..." calls back to his father's 1st

inaugural speech, specifically Marcos Sr.'s-"Our people have come to the point of despair," "I have heard your cries," and "I have seen it in our barrios, huts, and hovels all over the land" implying that the two presidents expressed their sensitivity to the country's problems and a factor as to why the two presidents had an appeal from the Filipinos that supported them. The current president's words were like a salve that soothed hearts that felt the loss of what they used to identify with: the national unity that Marcos Sr. had instilled in the Filipinos.

Additional utterances from Marcos Sr. showed that the theme of unity could be traced back to his father in the words and phrases, specifically "no Filipino... will be exempt," "never again stand in alienation," "build one nation," "unite, not divide," and "Filipino unity," to name a few. Those mentioned show polyphony from Bakhtin (1986), in which President Marcos Jr. expressed the importance of the nation's unity as his own.

Table 2 presents Marcos Jr.'s "...you rejected the politics of division," which further shows the strong influence of his father on his perspectives as a leader. In saying he was not an instrument of change but "You were that; you made it happen. I am now. You picked me to be your servant...." President Marcos Jr. accepted the people's will the way the late president attributed his leadership to the people's will: "...you have rejected all these through a new mandate of leadership...The voice of the masses is present, the Filipinos." Aside from the father's voice in the son's utterance, both their utterances also represented the voice of the Filipinos, which had been expressed through their votes. The use of 'your' and 'you' are present in both passages, suggesting that the Filipinos have a voice in this part. Bakhtin (1986) explains that an utterance reflects different speakers' ideas. Marcos Jr. uttered that passage to express that the choice for his leadership and how he presents himself is the result of the voices of the Filipinos.

Likewise, Table 3 shows how the son drove the nation toward action, mirrors the father's propelling words. Marcos Jr.'s "Come...give that wheel a faster turn" reminds of Marcos Sr.'s "Come...march together..." presented in Table 3. Marcos Jr.'s use of "radical change ...to recover what we have lost in the fire" echoes the nation's unity and the road to prosperity.

On the other hand, Table 4 is Marcos Jr.'s "We all want peace in our land," which upholds peace like his father did, as expressed in Marcos Sr.'s "Peace...we declare." Marcos Jr. also represented how Marcos Sr. expressed his sensitivity to people's dreams. This is presented as utterance pair number 7.

In Table 5, his utterance is polyphonic as it refers to the point of view of a defined source, which is his father, Marcos Sr. President Marcos Jr. said this in his speech, "Ang pangarap niyo ay pangarap ko," which also resembled what his father said in his inaugural speech –"This is your dream and mine.". To further support his sensitivity to the Filipino dream, the late Marcos Sr. gave importance to his vision of the dream Philippines being prosperous when he uttered, "Let us dream the vision." "...prove to our prosperity that our dream was true", and "redeeming every dream and aspiration." The "dream of prosperity" was addressed by Marcos Sr in the past, and it echoes what President Marcos

Jr is now doing; he is using his father's utterance, to make it his own. This shows that the dreams of President Marcos Jr and the late Marcos Sr are the same or in line with one another. In addition, there are utterances from Marcos Sr that are related to "dreams" but added that the president and Filipinos should not just dream but "achieve" as seen in "...not merely dream but we shall succeed" and "change not in dreams and aspirations... but in rededication and reappraisal".

Table 6 indicates another evidence of polyphony in utterance pair numbers #8 and #12. This shows the father's influence on the son in giving importance to agriculture. The father's consciousness concerning agriculture can be traced not only in his utterances but also in his Agrarian Reform Program known as Masagana 99 (Martial Law Museum n.d) (Anastacio & Abinales, 2022), which was meant to increase rice production through the use of new technology by farmers. The drive toward "rice self-sufficiency" in the past is echoed in the inaugural speech with the expressed aim for "food self-sufficiency.". When President Marcos Jr. said, "None but one delivered," he remembers how his father gave importance to agriculture. The late Marcos Sr highlighted the voice of the Filipino farmers in "We speak to our farming communities." and "Farmers...as leaseholders". The late president also gave his opinions and goals for agriculture during his time – "self-sufficiency...is a major goal", "we have succeeded in producing enough seeds," and the words "attaining" and "devoted."

Further, Table 7 presents Utterance 8, another evidence of polyphony. This utterance shows President Marcos Jr. talking about the education system of the Philippines; the president mentioned going back to the basics, not just history. Marcos Jr. values the education system of the Philippines and wants to improve it by emphasizing sciences, vocational skills, and global language.

By emphasizing not just history, it shows that the president acknowledges the opinions of the Filipinos about the past and his father, suggesting that "re-writing" history is not on the president's cards. Marcos Jr's utterance about the educational system echoes his father's utterance, "...providing an educational system which can tap the potentials and vitality of our human resources," which expressed concern about the current state of the education system, which leads to employment issues in the country. The utterance pair also echoes Marcos Sr's goals for national development from "Education is central..." in making the education system in the Philippines have more workforce skills as seen from the late president's utterance, "lower education adds little to the skilled manpower" then the two president's mentioned vocational skills / vocational schools; the two presidents showed their sensitivity to a longtime issue which is unemployment. The voice of the OFWs and future working Filipinos is present in this utterance as said by President Marcos Jr- "Let us give OFWs all the advantage we can for them to survive and to thrive" and "sharpening theoretical aptitude...vocational skills".

In addition to the topic of the education system of the Philippines, in utterance pair number 10. The utterance shows what the president thinks of the current situation of the Philippines. This shows the influence of Marcos Sr. on Marcos Jr. in giving concern to education. Marcos Sr.'s voice concerning school can be traced in his utterance. He

continues to experience difficulties in the past, which is restated in Marcos Jr's inaugural speech. The utterance calls back to utterance pair #8 concerning education. It mentioned "a past education system" that had future generations for more and better jobs. This is mentioning what was analyzed in utterance pair #8; to be more specific, it echoed the late Marcos Sr.'s vision of adding different skill sets in students to answer the shortage of jobs. Marcos Jr. and Sr. mention "vocational skills or schools."

In Table 8, 'No one was prepared for COVID-19 when it spread,' as expressed by Marcos Jr. in his inaugural speech. The president stated that the Philippines would become better prepared to address future issues and improve public health care under his watch. This is seen in utterance pair number 10, also from the utterance pair expressed by his father, "We shall strive to raise the efficiency of our public health service."; Marcos Sr. addressed health service because, at the time, different diseases were running rampant. Even if the technology advanced, many Filipinos needed more public health care. Marcos Jr. can express his sensitivity to Filipino health and safety, as seen in utterance pair 11. President Marcos Jr mentioned the struggles of Filipinos in public health during the pandemic and expressed his concerns. While Marcos Sr gave importance to the healthcare system and public health in his 2nd SONA by establishing The Malaria Eradication Program, increasing the staff and medical supply in rural areas, and deploying more medical staff in "barrios" and the "rural population." With these in mind, the voices of the needy Filipinos who do not have access to health care are present in this utterance pair. This relates to how Park-Fuller (2009) explained that polyphony is the ability of any utterance to convey another person's utterance while it is from the author, which then forms the dialogic relationship between the voices.

Moreover, Table 9 shows utterance 12, which mentions investors. It used the word "promising," which echoes his father's vision of the Philippines as a prosperous country for all: "We appeal to the businessmen of this country...". In this utterance, President Marcos Jr shared with the Filipinos that investors are already set up to help the Philippines flourish but emphasized that the full potential of the Philippines is not yet reached. This is similar to how his father addressed the investors and business people in his utterances, where Marcos Sr welcomes Filipino investors and investors from abroad in the Philippines. This implies that his father's goal of welcoming local and foreign investors to do business in the Philippines is also the intention of President Marcos Jr.

For Table 10, utterance 13 was presented. President Marcos Jr. directly mentioned his father by saying he built better roads and produced more rice than other administrations. President Marcos Jr. implies that his father's infrastructure and rice production contributions are unmatched. The way Marcos Jr. is aware shows similarity to how Marcos Sr. expressed awareness of his accomplishments, judging from Marcos Sr.'s multiple utterances about his infrastructure and rice production programs.

As seen in Table 11, President Marcos Jr talked about the nation being safer and more prosperous. His utterances show the polyphony and how it echoes Marcos Sr's vision for a prosperous road in the Philippines. Marcos Jr echoes what he and his father saw in the Philippines as a struggling nation, as seen in utterance 14. It is shown in how

Filipinos vote on who they believe can lead the country in the coming years. This utterance 14 shows the different utterances of Marcos Sr, who projected the voices of the masses.

Similarly, Table 12 indicates that the Filipinos cried for change; President Marcos Jr also mentioned "politics of division." This implies that even the government and the Filipinos are not united as a nation, which explains why President Marcos Jr uttered, "Imagine what you and the government can achieve together." The essence of the government and the citizens working together, being united is echoed in the utterances from Marcos Sr in utterance pair #15, in which Marcos Sr mentioned 1- the government is a servant to the nation's dream and needs, 2- planning new concepts that emphasizes the cooperation and interaction between the office and its people, and 3 – the initiative of the Filipinos together with the government will determine what can the nation accomplish. Overall, this utterance pair goes back to the president's theme of unity.

Equally important, Table 13 presents Utterance 16, which sees President Marcos Jr saying, "...let us march together towards the dream of greatness." After analyzing the utterances shown in Table 1, the final sentence in his inaugural speech sums up what he intends to do. Combining what was analyzed, it is implied that the mention of "what was lost in the fire" is referring to what the late Marcos Sr envisioned for the Philippines, which can be seen in utterance pair #16 as "let us cross this frontier," "march together towards the dream of greatness," "a future which will be bright and prosperous," etc. The road of prosperity implied during his father's time was lost in the fire.

Lastly, Table 14 presents Utterance pairs 17, 18, and 19 when President Marcos Jr mentions the last president to take office, former President Duterte, and acknowledges or gives respect to the last president and thanks him for his efforts. This implies that President Marcos Jr sees former President Duterte as one of the presidents who were the "strongman" in the country, the first one being the late Marcos Sr. Thompson (2022) titled THE DECLINE OF THE YELLOWS AND THE RETURN OF STRONGMAN RULE from the book *The Marcos Era A Reader*. The article talked about the decline of the Yellows; in this period, Aquino's preferred successor, Manuel "Mar" Roxas II, lost to the 'strongman' Rodrigo Roa Duterte. It was also compared to how Donald Trump beat Hillary Clinton in the US presidential campaign in the same year. Thompson also discussed that Duterte effectively portrayed Roxas as "incompetent, soft on crime, and out of touch with ordinary people." Roxas also approached using liberal reformism, which was also used by the Aquinos and Ramos, to a successful effect. Still, in the case of the 2016 election, Roxas' attempts did not gain the population's attention and support. Thompson continued to explain that the outcome was the Filipino seeing Roxas' attempt as insincere and self-righteous. The yellows also promised the Filipinos that they would eradicate corruption, which they argued would end poverty, as seen in Noynoy's campaign slogan in 2010, "When there is no corruption, there will be no poverty."

Essentially, utterance pair 19 shows Marcos Jr. praising Filipino nurses. The articles from Alibudbud (2022) and Chia and Tolentino (2021) illustrate what Filipino nurses felt and went through during the pandemic. Marcos Jr.'s mention of the nurses in

the Philippines reflects the consciousness of our nurses. They know how valuable they are everywhere and that they are worth more.

Intentions to Including Other Voices in the Speech

President Marcos Jr.'s utterances revealed his call and intention for peace. Besides, in utterances 8 and 13 is where President Marcos Jr mentioned his take on the current state of agriculture and his concerns, together with mentioning his father in "None but one delivered," "My father built more and better roads...more rice", his calls back to his father as a way to remember the goals and accomplishments set out my father. The mention of these could solidify that the late Marcos' legacy is unmatched.

The utterance-"Our nurses are the best in the world..." was to emphasize that Filipino nurses are valued abroad for their dedication and paid better abroad than in the Philippines. President Marcos Jr emphasized Filipino nurses' importance and value by saying they were underpaid for their risks and dedication amidst the pandemic. According to Alibudbud (2022), they discussed the migration and resignation of Filipino nurses during the COVID-19 pandemic. Alibudbud's paper mentioned that the first year of the pandemic showed Filipino nurses resigning and then moving to work abroad. The result was that hospitals suffered downsizing in their staff due to the lack of healthcare workers. Filipino nurses were praised as heroes during the pandemic; they were respected and honored better. They were at constant risk every day and exhausted.

President Marcos Jr mentioned in his inaugural speech-"Investors are now setting up industries along the promising routes built." The utterance informs the country that investors are talking with the government to set up existing businesses or projects from past administrations. This is supported by the previous paragraph, where he mentioned the roads and rice his father produced and the projects of former president Duterte. To further support this, we look at the paragraph after "Investors..." where President Marcos Jr mentioned, "We will continue to build," and "I am not interested in taking credit."

Additionally, "I want to build on the success already happening." This implies that President Marcos Jr plans to improve the successful projects and programs that other people started. The mention of his father and Duterte implies that those two former presidents are his basis in developing the country for years to come.

Conclusions

The researchers discovered that the presence of voices in the inaugural speech of President Marcos Jr. displayed polyphony, as claimed by Bakhtin, similar to how Cabaysa (2016) revealed that the voice of Grace Poe's adoptive father's voice is predominantly present as well as the presence of other voices. What makes a speech polyphonic is when there are traceable intentions or thoughts from the speaker and embedded markers indicating explicit or implicit clues in the utterance. Based on the results, the researchers concluded that the alignment of the utterances from Marcos Jr. shows that the influence and intention of his father are connected to that of the president.

Recommendations

Since the study was limited to Marcos Sr.'s inaugural speech as the basis of analysis, other speeches from his mother and politicians must be considered for more valid polyphonic speeches and results.

Future studies could involve various voices from different intensive speeches not limited to one type.

Lastly, it is essential to note that including polyphonic markers can significantly enhance the results' conclusiveness.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study analyzed the polyphony in President Marcos Jr.'s Inaugural speech. It is essential to declare that this paper, while a unique contribution, respects and does not intend to plagiarize previous interpretative works that are similar in structure and came before it. The researchers cited and referenced the indicated ideas and sources to achieve this intention. Suppose any section of this paper is deemed to have instances of plagiarism. In that case, the researchers are open to comments, suggestions, and revisions to follow the code of ethics that comes with scholarly writing.

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